

Fit Transfer Function

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1 Create parametric models from frequency response analysis in PLECS

The motivation of this tutorial is to bridge the gap between frequency response measurements collected from the Analysis Tools in PLECS (for example a *Multitone Analysis*) and a model-based design of a controller.

This tutorial uses the *Half-Bridge LLC Converter with Analysis Tools* from the PLECS demo models. The description can be found on the Plexim GmbH website at [half_bridge_llc_converter_with_analysis_tools.pdf](#) or in the PLECS manual. There is also a video explaining the model at [demo-model-video-plecs-half-bridge-llc-analysis](#).

It is challenging to derive a linear system description from this model. The reason for that is that the output voltage is controlled by varying the switching frequency and not by varying the duty cycle. However, it is possible to apply a *Multitone Analysis* in the operating point for the nominal output voltage of 12 V.

The analysis is already set up in the demo model. The compensator design is based on the loop shaping technique using poles, zeros, and a loop gain to set the cross-over frequency of around 700Hz with suitable gain and phase margins. Because the model is not analytic, stability has to be shown using the Nyquist criterium.

In this tutorial, we show a way of converting the data from the *Multitone Analysis* (or other frequency response measurements) to a parametric model, i.e. a transfer function. This model will support the compensator design by giving instant information about stability, closed loop performance, and robustness measures.

1.1 Run Analysis Tools to collect data

The first task is collecting the data. This can be done using the built-in scripting possibilities in PLECS by running some Octave commands. Because collecting data runs the *Analysis Tool*, this step may take several seconds. Therefore, it is good practice to first store the data and then run the identification and plotting code afterwards, by loading the stored data.

According to the PLECS manual, to run the *Analysis Tool* and store the data in Octave, use a *Simulation script* that looks like

```
data = plecs('analyze', 'OpenLoopAnalysis');  
f = data.F;  
r = data.Gr + 1j*data.Gi;
```

```
save('G.mat', '-mat', 'f', 'r');
```

To generate the data from python, make sure that the RPC interface is enabled in the PLECS preferences and run

```
[1]: import xmlrpc.client
import numpy as np

from os import getcwd
from scipy.io import savemat

mdlName = "half_bridge_llc_converter_with_analysis_tools"

plecs = xmlrpc.client.ServerProxy("http://localhost:1080").plecs
plecs.load(getcwd() + "\\\" + mdlName + ".plecs")
data = plecs.analyze(mdlName, "OpenLoopAnalysis")

f = np.array(data["F"])
r = np.array(data["Gr"][0]) + 1j*np.array(data["Gi"][0])

savemat("G.mat", {"f": f, "r": r})
```

1.2 Load and visualize data

After collecting and storing the data (either in a *Simulation script* or python), you can load and visualise it. For that we use the *Python Control Systems Library*, which has a nice *bode* plot included

```
[2]: from scipy.io import loadmat
from numpy import pi
import control
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

data = loadmat('G.mat')
f = data["f"][0]
r = data["r"][0]

w = 2*pi*f
G = control.frd(r, w)

_ = control.bode_plot(G, w, Hz=True)
```


1.3 Fit a transfer function

1.3.1 Fitting by hand

From this point, you can start to fit a transfer function by hand. The frequency response looks like a second-order system with a damped resonant frequency around $f_0 = 5.5$ kHz and a zero around $s_0 = 8$ kHz

```
[3]: w0 = 5.5e3*2*pi
d = 0.55
K = -0.6
s0 = 8e3*2*pi
Gm1 = control.tf(K*w0**2, [1, 2*d*w0, w0**2]) * control.tf([1/s0, 1], 1)
_ = control.bode_plot((G, Gm1), w, Hz=True)
```


This model already fits the data quite well. With a little more effort, the phase can be improved for higher frequencies.

Fitting by hand can lead to acceptable results for many other experiments with frequency response measurements.

1.3.2 Automatic fitting

Fitting by hand of course has its limits. If you need an automatically fitted transfer function, one way is to formulate a least square problem based on the frequency response data and a transfer function $G(s)$, with a defined order of the numerator m and denominator n according to

$$G(s) = \frac{b_n s^m + b_{m-1} s^{m-1} + \dots + b_0}{s^n + a_{n-1} s^{n-1} + \dots + a_0}.$$

For each measured frequency ω_k from the Analysis Tool, this can be put into the following form:

$$G(j\omega_k) = \frac{b_n (j\omega_k)^m + b_{m-1} (j\omega_k)^{m-1} + \dots + b_0}{(j\omega_k)^n + a_{n-1} (j\omega_k)^{n-1} + \dots + a_0} \quad (1)$$

and rearranging (1) leads to

$$G(j\omega_k) \cdot (j\omega_k)^n = b_n (j\omega_k)^m + b_{m-1} (j\omega_k)^{m-1} + \dots + b_0 - G(j\omega_k) \cdot (a_{n-1} (j\omega_k)^{n-1} + \dots + a_0). \quad (2)$$

Note that (2) is linear in the parameters $a_0 \dots a_n$ and $b_0 \dots b_n$ and can be rearranged to a scalar product of two vectors

$$G(j\omega_k) \cdot (j\omega_k)^n = \begin{bmatrix} (j\omega_k)^m & (j\omega_k)^{m-1} & \dots & 1 & -G(j\omega_k) \cdot (j\omega_k)^{n-1} & \dots & -G(j\omega_k) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} b_m \\ b_{m-1} \\ \vdots \\ b_0 \\ a_{n-1} \\ \vdots \\ a_0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Stacking all equations for all frequencies ω_k for $k = 1 \dots H$ results in

$$\begin{bmatrix} G(j\omega_1) \cdot (j\omega_1)^n \\ \vdots \\ G(j\omega_H) \cdot (j\omega_H)^n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (j\omega_1)^m & (j\omega_1)^{m-1} & \dots & 1 & -G(j\omega_1) \cdot (j\omega_1)^{n-1} & \dots & -G(j\omega_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (j\omega_H)^m & (j\omega_H)^{m-1} & \dots & 1 & -G(j\omega_H) \cdot (j\omega_H)^{n-1} & \dots & -G(j\omega_H) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} b_m \\ b_{m-1} \\ \vdots \\ b_0 \\ a_{n-1} \\ \vdots \\ a_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

or in short form

$$\mathbf{Y}_c = \mathbf{X}_c \cdot \mathbf{c}_c.$$

Because \mathbf{X}_c and \mathbf{Y}_c are both matrices with complex values, the vector \mathbf{c}_c will in general also be a complex-valued vector. We want to avoid this and force the solution to be real-valued by solving the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X} &= \begin{bmatrix} \Re(\mathbf{X}_c) \\ \Im(\mathbf{X}_c) \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{Y} &= \begin{bmatrix} \Re(\mathbf{Y}_c) \\ \Im(\mathbf{Y}_c) \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{Y} &= \mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{c} \end{aligned}$$

The least square solution \mathbf{c} minimizes the 2-norm $\|\mathbf{Y} - \mathbf{X} \cdot \mathbf{c}\|$ and can be calculated in Octave with the command

```
c = X\Y;
```

In python, there is the function `numpy.linalg.lstsq`. Building the matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} and solving for \mathbf{c} (the numerator and denominator coefficients) can be packed into a function:

```
[4]: def fit_transfer_function(r, w, m, n):
      assert m <= n
      H = len(r)
```

```

jw = 1j*w

Yc = np.full((H, 1), 1j*np.NaN)
Xc = np.full((H, m+n+1), 1j*np.NaN)

for k in range(H):
    Gjw = r[k]
    Yc[k] = Gjw*jw[k]**n
    for i in range(0, m+1):
        Xc[k, i] = jw[k]**(m-i)
    for i in range(1, n+1):
        Xc[k, m+i] = -Gjw*jw[k]**(n-i)

Y = np.vstack((np.real(Yc), np.imag(Yc)))
X = np.vstack((np.real(Xc), np.imag(Xc)))

c = list(np.linalg.lstsq(X, Y, rcond=None)[0].T[0])
b = c[:m+1]
a = [1] + c[m+1:]
return (b, a)

```

Now, we can fit a second order system ($n = 2$) with one zero ($m = 1$) and compare the result with the hand-fitted transfer function

```

[5]: b, a = fit_transfer_function(r, w, 1, 2)
      Gm2 = control.tf(b, a)
      _ = control.bode_plot((G, Gm2), w, Hz=True)

```


This solution looks very similar to the hand-fitted transfer function. The main difference is that the fitting error is distributed over the whole frequency range and not mainly in the high frequency range.

With the fitting algorithm at hand, we can quickly compare different models by varying the number of numerator m and denominator n coefficients. By increasing the order of the numerator m from 1 to 2, we get an almost perfect fit.

```
[6]: b, a = fit_transfer_function(r, w, 2, 2)
      Gm3 = control.tf(b, a)
      _ = control.bode_plot((G, Gm3), G.omega, Hz=True)
```


If you want to improve the model also for the lower frequency range by increasing m and n , the model becomes worse

```
[7]: b, a = fit_transfer_function(r, w, 3, 3)
      Gm4 = control.tf(b, a)
      _ = control.bode_plot((G, Gm4), G.omega, Hz=True)
```


This behaviour can have various causes (overfitting, bad matrix condition numbers, inappropriate model, etc.). Furthermore, the method does not work very well for real measured data with noise. This tutorial does not address these issues and refers to the literature, for example:

[1] Ljung, Lennart (2012): System identification. Theory for the user. 2. ed., 14. printing. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall (Prentice-Hall information and system sciences series).

[2] Isermann, Rolf; Münchhof, Marco (2014): Identification of Dynamic Systems. An Introduction with Applications. Aufl. 2011. Berlin: Springer Berlin.

[3] Hrycej, Tomas (2018): Robuste Regelung. Ein Leitfadens für sicherheitskritische Anwendungen. 1. Auflage 2018. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

[4] Benner, Peter; Grivet-Talocia, Stefano; Quarteroni, Alfio; Rozza, Gianluigi; Schilders, Wil; Silveira, Luís Miguel (Hg.) (2021): System- and Data-Driven Methods and Algorithms: De Gruyter.

1.4 Compensator verification

The compensator used in the simulation is defined as

```
[8]: wp0 = 3.2e3
wp1 = 2*pi*8.2e3
wz1 = 2*pi*4.2e3
pole0 = control.tf(wp0, (1, 0))
pole_zero1 = control.tf((1/wz1, 1), (1/wp1, 1))
Gr = -3/1.28255 * pole_zero1 * pole0
_ = control.bode_plot(Gr, w, Hz=True)
```


To compare the loop gain of the identified model and the compensator with the measured loop gain in PLECS, two modifications are required in the controller $G_r(s)$

- the open loop measurements have an additional gain to convert the voltage reference to a frequency ($V_{ref} \rightarrow freq$ block)
- there is an additional negative sign in the loop to compensate the negative sign of the plant: increasing the switching frequency will reduce the output voltage.

These are the reasons for the additional controller gain of $-3/1.28255$.

The calculated loop gain becomes

```
[9]: Lm = Gm3*Gr
```

The measured loop gain from the *Analysis Tool* can be stored in the same way as for the open loop plant and then loaded and compared with the calculated loop gain

```
[10]: data = loadmat('L.mat')
L = control.frd(data["r"][0], data["f"][0]*2*pi)
_ = control.bode_plot((L, Lm), w, Hz=True)
```


With the model, we can test the voltage tracking behaviour $T(s)$

```
[11]: T = control.feedback(Lm, 1)
      _ = control.bode_plot(T, w, Hz=True)
```



```
[12]: t, y = control.step_response(T)
_ = plt.plot(t*1e3, y)
plt.grid('on')
_ = plt.xlabel('Time [ms]')
_ = plt.ylabel('Step Response  $T(s)$  [V]')
```


and the disturbance rejection or sensitivity $S(s)$ of the control system

```
[13]: S = control.feedback(1, Lm)
_ = control.bode_plot(S, w, Hz=True, initial_phase=90)
```



```
[14]: t, y = control.step_response(S)
_ = plt.plot(t*1e3, y)
plt.grid('on')
_ = plt.xlabel('Time [ms]')
_ = plt.ylabel('Step Response  $S(s)$  [V]')
```


1.5 Conclusion

For controller design, it is often desirable to have a linear model of the plant in an operating point. This tutorial showed how you can get such a model systematically from frequency response measurements. The provided fitting function `fit_transfer_function(r, w, m, n)` requires only the measurements and the orders of the numerator and denominator of the desired transfer function.